

Model Profiles: Descriptive Characterization Across the Framework Dimensions

A Decision Framework for Selecting Technology Acceptance and Use Models: TAM, TAM2, TAM3, UTAUT, and UTAUT2

Anonymized for peer review

The five profiles presented below characterize the models TAM, TAM2, TAM3, UTAUT, and UTAUT2 across the five analytical dimensions (D1–D5) that compose the proposed framework. These profiles were derived through a concept-centric synthesis process (Webster & Watson, 2002) grounded in Design Science Research principles (Hevner et al., 2004).

The derivation followed a structured pipeline: (i) systematic extraction of theoretical elements from the five foundational articles (Davis, 1989; Venkatesh & Davis, 2000; Venkatesh & Bala, 2008; Venkatesh et al., 2003; Venkatesh, Thong & Xu, 2012); (ii) coding and grouping into conceptual dimensions informed by five critical reviews (Turner et al., 2010; Williams et al., 2015; De Brito & Ramos, 2019; Malatji et al., 2020; Batista et al., 2023) and three theoretical antecedents (TRA, TPB, IDT); (iii) structural comparison through a model-by-dimension matrix, from which nine initial attributes were consolidated into the five discriminating dimensions D1–D5; and (iv) organization of each model's positioning across these dimensions as descriptive profiles, following the conceptual framework construction procedure proposed by Jabareen (2009).

Each profile synthesizes how a given model is situated along the five dimensions, enabling researchers to assess theoretical alignment before model selection. The profiles operate as Component 3 of the framework and are intended to support, not replace, the researcher's informed judgment.

Profile 1: TAM

D1. Application Context: Contexts in which the focus falls predominantly on the individual user's relationship with the technology, with extensive use in organizational settings.

D2. Intended Type of Use: Voluntary or mandatory, with no explicit distinction between use regimes. The model does not operationalize this difference.

D3. Adoption Stage: Initial acceptance, focused on the formation of behavioral intention to use. It does not incorporate mechanisms for addressing continued use or habit.

D4. Explanatory Focus: Strictly cognitive-instrumental, centered on perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. It does not incorporate social influence or affective elements as core constructs.

D5. Intended Analytical Granularity: Low. Parsimonious structure with two core constructs.

Profile 2: TAM2

D1. Application Context: Organizational, with a strong connection to workplace settings. The model incorporates constructs directly associated with the work task (job relevance, output quality, result demonstrability).

D2. Intended Type of Use: Explicitly distinguishes between voluntary and mandatory use. Voluntariness operates as a moderator of social influence, making the model particularly relevant in mandatory use scenarios.

D3. Adoption Stage: Initial acceptance, with emphasis on the formation of behavioral intention in organizational contexts. Experience acts as a moderator, but the focus remains on acceptance.

D4. Explanatory Focus: Cognitive-instrumental, extended by social influence in normative forms (subjective norm, image) and instrumental processes associated with the task. Social influence is a core construct.

D5. Intended Analytical Granularity: Intermediate. Extends the TAM structure with controlled parsimony, without departing from its fundamental logic.

Profile 3: TAM3

D1. Application Context: Organizational, especially in scenarios requiring a detailed understanding of use barriers and technology interaction conditions.

D2. Intended Type of Use: Voluntary or mandatory, with less emphasis on the distinction between **use** regimes than on the influence of accumulated experience on the constructs.

D3. Adoption Stage: Acceptance and variations in use perceptions as a function of accumulated experience. Experience moderates the relationships between antecedents and perceived ease of use over time, enabling the capture of changes arising from familiarity.

D4. Explanatory Focus: Cognitive-instrumental, extended by individual, affective, and perceptual antecedents of perceived ease of use, organized through an anchoring-and-adjustment logic. It incorporates affective elements as antecedents of ease of use, but not as direct determinants of intention.

D5. Intended Analytical Granularity: High. Dense structure with multiple detailed antecedents of perceived ease of use, requiring greater operationalization effort.

Profile 4: UTAUT

D1. Application Context: Organizational, oriented toward job performance, infrastructure, and individual heterogeneity.

D2. Intended Type of Use: Voluntary and mandatory, with explicit incorporation of voluntariness of use as a moderator of specific construct relationships.

D3. Adoption Stage: Acceptance and use. Articulates behavioral intention and actual use behavior, considering moderators that operate in the transition between them. Facilitating conditions directly influence use behavior.

D4. Explanatory Focus: Multiple determinants articulated in an integrated structure, encompassing performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions. Social influence is broadly formulated as expectations regarding technology use by relevant others.

D5. Intended Analytical Granularity: High. Combines multiple constructs and four moderators (gender, age, experience, voluntariness of use) in a comprehensive formulation.

Profile 5: UTAUT2

D1. Application Context: Individual consumer context. Explicit shift from the organizational context to personal, voluntary use oriented by the consumer experience.

D2. Intended Type of Use: Predominantly voluntary, with the exclusion of voluntariness as a moderator due to the predominantly voluntary nature of the consumer context.

D3. Adoption Stage: Acceptance, use, and continuance, with particular sensitivity to consolidated use patterns. It incorporates habit as a direct determinant of both intention and use behavior.

D4. Explanatory Focus: Multiple determinants in an integrated structure, augmented by hedonic motivation, price value, and habit. Social influence is retained but repositioned within a voluntary consumer context. Exhibits explicit sensitivity to hedonic and non-instrumental behavioral elements.

D5. Intended Analytical Granularity: High. Expansion of UTAUT with three additional constructs and moderators for gender, age, and experience.

Key References for Profile Derivation

Foundational articles: Davis (1989); Venkatesh & Davis (2000); Venkatesh et al. (2003); Venkatesh & Bala (2008); Venkatesh, Thong & Xu (2012).

Critical reviews (secondary corpus): Turner et al. (2010); Williams et al. (2015); De Brito & Ramos (2019); Malatji et al. (2020); Batista et al. (2023).

Theoretical antecedents: Theory of Reasoned Action (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975); Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991); Innovation Diffusion Theory (Rogers, 1983).

Methodological grounding: Webster & Watson (2002); Jabareen (2009); Hevner et al. (2004).